

Synthesis, characterization and structure of pentadentate azoimine ligand and its dinuclear copper complex[†]

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Abstract : The new protonated form of pentadentate ligand [H₂L]ClO₄, **1**, was synthesized by metal assisted template pathway. Reaction of 2,6-diformyl-4-methyl phenol and 2-(*p*-chloro phenyl) azo aniline in presence of zinc perchlorate afforded **1**. New dinuclear [(L)₂Cu₂](ClO₄)₂, **2**, complex was prepared by the reaction of [H₂L]ClO₄, **1** with Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O. Also the [(L)₂Cu₂](ClO₄)₂, **2**, complex was isolated upon reaction of 2,6-diformyl-4-methyl phenol, 2-(*p*-chloro phenyl) azo aniline and Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O in one pot. The Cu^{II} centres of dinuclear [(L)₂Cu₂](ClO₄)₂ complex were antiferromagnetically coupled. X-Ray structures of [H₂L]ClO₄ ligand and [(L)₂Cu₂](ClO₄)₂ complex were determined to confirm the molecular species unequivocally.

Keywords : Pentadentate ligand, dinuclear Cu^{II} complexes, X-ray structures.

Introduction

Studies on copper(II) complexes have been widely explored for the versatility of their coordination geometries, exquisite colours, technical applications depending on molecular structures, redox and spectroscopic properties and their biological significances¹⁻¹⁴. Copper(II) complexes of ligands containing mixed electron donors have been studied extensively due to their interesting properties such as electrical conductivity, magnetic property, photochromism and photoluminescence, nonlinear optical property, and antimicrobial activity¹⁻¹⁴. Among various ligands, azo ligands containing azoimine (-N=N-C=N-) linkage of π -acidic N,N'-chelating systems and their coordination chemistry is presently an active area in current chemical research¹⁵⁻³⁰. The azoimine function has specialty to stabilize lower oxidation states of metal ions and tune the redox and spectroscopic properties of the metal centre. There are reports where the mesomorphism and liquid crystalline properties of some copper complexes were derived from azo-linked salicylaldehyde homologues³¹. The blue luminescent dichloro-bridged dinuclear copper(II) complex with salicylaldehyde 2-pyridyl hydrazone ligand exhibits a strong interaction

towards DNA, quasireversible one-electron oxidation in aqueous medium and cytotoxic effect³². The dinuclear copper(II) complexes of pyridyl-containing azo ligands catalyze aerial oxidation of L-ascorbic acid³³. The mono, di, and polynuclear copper(II) complexes act as efficient and selective catalysts³⁴. A few chromoionophores based on azobenzene have been reported for copper(II) ions³⁵.

The azoimine function containing organic compounds have been employed as ligands to synthesize important and interesting metal chelates. Incorporation of arylazo groups (Ar-N=N-) into the backbone of N-heterocycle at the *ortho* position has lead to the synthesis of arylazo-heterocycles with azoimine function. These ligands have been used as potential ligand. A group of these ligands are shown below (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

We planned to synthesize a new type of azoimine ligands in which the imine group (-C=N-) does belong to the heterocyclic backbone, **I**. These new class of azoimine ligands are different from the ligand type, shown in Scheme 1, with respect to the imine function and the extended

delocalization over the azo and imine function. Due to more extensive delocalization, these ligands, **I**, may not only possess the properties compared to that of the ligand type (Scheme 1) but also there are possibilities to obtain new interesting characteristics.

Herein we describe the synthesis, characterization and structure of binuclear copper(II) complexes incorporating azoimine ligands, **I**.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

There are many condensation processes between aldehyde and amine to form aldimine linkage (Schiff's base). The azoimine compounds, **A**, were formed, when 2,6-

diformyl-4-methyl phenol and 2-aryazo aniline were refluxed in diethylether³⁶. Therefore we attempted to synthesize the doubly condensed product, **1**, by template method i.e. the reaction of 2,6-diformyl-4-methyl phenol with 2-(aryazo)aniline was carried out in presence of $Zn(ClO_4)_2$ [eq. (1)]. The attempt was successful and the perchlorate salt of protonated pentadentate ligand $[H_2L]ClO_4$, **1**, was isolated [eq. (2)]. The reddish brown crystalline product was isolated after evaporating the solvent.

The new copper complex, $[(L)_2Cu_2](ClO_4)_2$, **2**, was synthesized by the reaction of $[H_2L]ClO_4$, **1**, and copper perchlorate in methanol in presence of triethylamine. This complex can also be prepared in one pot by refluxing 2,6-diformyl-4-methyl phenol, 2-(*p*-chloro arylazo)aniline and copper perchlorate are to be refluxed in methanol. Synthetic reaction is shown below (Scheme 2). The dinuclear complex was characterized unequivocally by X-ray studies (see below).

Characterization :

The dichloromethane solution of $[H_2L]ClO_4$ ligand displayed characteristic UV-Vis spectra comprising the low energy band at 525 nm which was absent in the $[(L)_2Cu](ClO_4)_2$ complex. Other two absorptions (at 365 and 310 nm) of $[H_2L]ClO_4$ shifted slightly to higher energy (360 and 295 nm) for $[(L)_2Cu](ClO_4)_2$ complex. The UV-Vis spectra of the ligand and complex have been

Scheme 2

shown in Figs. S1 and S2.

ν_{ClO_4} of $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]\text{ClO}_4$ and $[(\text{L})_2\text{Cu}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ appeared at 1085 cm^{-1} signifying the presence of perchlorate ion in $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]\text{ClO}_4$ and presence of uncoordinated perchlorate ion in $[(\text{L})_2\text{Cu}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]\text{ClO}_4$ (1638 cm^{-1}) shifted toward lower energy (1616 cm^{-1}) for $[(\text{L})_2\text{Cu}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ complexes indicating coordination of aldimine nitrogens¹⁹⁻²¹. The $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ of the ligands (1450 cm^{-1}) did not shift for $[(\text{L})_2\text{Cu}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ complexes which signified that the azo nitrogen did not coordinate the metal centre. The IR spectra of the ligand and complex have been shown in Figs. S3 and S4.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of the $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]\text{ClO}_4$ ligand exhibited resonances at δ 11.39 and 10.15 for phenolic OH and aldimine ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) functions. Although resonances for other aromatic protons appeared as complicated overlapped signals but matched well with the total number of protons. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the ligand has been shown in Fig. S5.

X-Ray structure :

Suitable crystals of $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]\text{ClO}_4$, **1** and $[(\text{L})_2\text{Cu}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, **2** for X-ray studies were grown by slow diffusion of hexane into the dichloromethane solution. The X-ray structure of $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]\text{ClO}_4$ exhibited presence of one perchlorate ion in the asymmetric unit. The perspective view of the

protonated $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]^+$ and $[(\text{L})_2\text{Cu}_2]^{2+}$ cations have been shown with atom numbering scheme in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Only two protons H1a and H1b are shown for $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]^+$,

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]^+$ with atom numbering scheme. Hydrogen atoms, excepting H1a and H1b have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 2. (a) Molecular structure of $[(L)_2Cu_2]^+$ with atom numbering scheme. Hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity. (b) The coordination sphere of $[(L)_2Cu_2]^+$ showing the distal Cu-N(azo) interactions.

all other protons were omitted for clarity. H1a and H1b protons were located by Fourier mapping to identify the protonated site of $[H_2L]^+$. Both, H1a and H1b, were hydrogen bonded between aldimino nitrogen (N1 and N4) and phenolic oxygen (O5) in $[H_2L]^+$. The deprotonated pentadentate ligand, L^- , coordinated each of the Cu^{II} ions of dinuclear $[(L)_2Cu_2](ClO_4)_2$ complex through two aldimine nitrogens and two bridging μ_2 -phenolato oxygens. The geometry around the each Cu atom was distorted tetrahedral. The Cu-O-Cu angles in the dinuclear assembly were 102 and 103° consistent with the antiferromagnetically coupled Cu^{II} centres³⁷. The azo ($-N=N-$) nitrogens are held at distal positions (range 2.656–2.831 Å) from the Cu^{II} ions.

Experimental

Materials :

All commercially available chemicals and solvents utilized in the present work were of analytical grade and the most of the cases these were used as obtained. The chemicals and their sources were as follows : *o*-phenylenediamine, *p*-chloronitrobenzene, Loba (India); sodium hydroxide, nitrobenzene, sulfuric acid, diethyl ether, E.

Merck (India); benzene, dichloromethane, acetonitrile, methanol, petroleum ether, silica gel (60–120 mesh), Rankem (India).

Physical measurements :

Microanalysis (C, H, N) was performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 C, H, N, S/O series II elemental analyzer. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer L120-00A FT-IR spectrometer with the samples prepared as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1800 PC spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR data were collected in $CDCl_3$ solvent with the help of Bruker-Advance DPX 400 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard.

Preparation of ligands $[H_2L]ClO_4$, **1** :

To a 60 ml methanolic solution of 0.164 g (1 mmol) of 2,6-diformyl-4-methyl phenol, 0.372 g (1 mmol) zinc perchlorate salt was added and it was boiled for 10 min. The solution turned greenish color. To this solution 0.463 g (2 mmol) of 2- $\{(4\text{-chloro})\text{phenylazo}\}$ aniline was added and it was boiled for another 30 min. The solution turned pink-red color. Then this was kept for dryness. After evaporation, the pink-red colored crystals were obtained

in the bottom of the round bottle. Yield : 73%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{33}H_{25}N_6O_5Cl_3$: C, 57.26; H, 3.61; N, 12.14. Found : C, 57.30; H, 3.65; N, 12.10%; UV/Vis spectrum (CH_2Cl_2) λ_{max} (ϵ , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) : 525 (8820), 365^{sh} (25000), 311 (31900); IR (KBr pellets, cm^{-1}) : ν 1450 (N=N), 1638 (C=N), 1085 (ClO_4); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 11.39 (1H, s, OH), 10.15 (2H, s, CH=N), 7.80–7.70 (6H, m, ArH), 7.48 (2H, d, ArH), 7.38 (4H, d, ArH), 7.16 (2H, t, ArH), 6.78–6.74 (4H, m, ArH), 2.36 (3H, s, CH_3).

Preparation of complexes $[(L)_2Cu_2](ClO_4)_2$, 2 :

In methanolic solution of 0.691 g (1 mmol) of $[H_2L]ClO_4$ ligand, 0.507 g (1 mmol) $Cu(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was added. The mixture was stirred for 3.5 h after adding triethylamine. A grayish precipitate was obtained. It was dissolved in dichloromethane to form deep brown color and layered with hexane in a test tube. From this fine crystal were collected after evaporating the solvent. The yield was 72%. Anal. Calcd. for $[Cu_2C_{66}H_{46}N_{12}O_{10}Cl_6]$: C, 52.58; H, 3.05; N, 11.15. Found : C, 52.50; H, 3.10; N, 11.20%; UV/Vis spectrum (CH_2Cl_2) λ_{max} (ϵ , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) : 432^{sh} (17200), 360^{sh} (73400), 295 (112000); IR (KBr pellets, cm^{-1}) : ν 1450

(N=N), 1616 (C=N), 1087 (ClO_4).

This $[(L)_2Cu_2](ClO_4)_2$, 2, complex can also be prepared directly in one pot. In this process, the methanolic solution of 0.164 g (1 mmol) of 2,6-diformyl-4-methyl phenol and 0.335 g (1 mmol) $Cu(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was boiled for 10 min. The solution gave yellowish brown color. To this solution 0.463 g (2 mmol) of 2-{(4-chloro)phenylazo}-aniline was added and the mixture was refluxed for 30 min. Brownish precipitate was obtained. After dissolving the precipitate in dichloromethane, it was layered with hexane in a test tube. Fine crystals were obtained from this after evaporating the solvent.

X-Ray structure determination of $[H_2L]ClO_4$ and $[(L)_2Cu_2](ClO_4)_2$:

Single crystals of $[H_2L]ClO_4$ and $[(L)_2Cu_2](ClO_4)_2$ were grown by slow diffusion of hexane in dichloromethane solution at 25 °C. Data were collected on a Bruker SMART CCD diffractometer using Mo-K α monochromator ($\lambda = 0.71073$). Structure solutions were performed using SHELX 97 PC version program³⁸. Full matrix least square refinements on F2 were performed using SHELXL-97 program³⁹. All the non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically using full-matrix least squares

Table 1. Crystallographic data for $[H_2L]ClO_4$ and $[(L)_2Cu_2](ClO_4)_2$

Chemical formula	$C_{33}H_{25}Cl_2N_6O \cdot ClO_4$	$C_{66}H_{46}Cl_4Cu_2N_{12}O_2 \cdot 2(ClO_4)$
Formula weight	691.94	1506.95
Crystal system	Triclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	P-1 (No. 2)	C2/c (No. 15)
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.669(3)	19.0025(5)
<i>b</i> (Å)	12.762(3)	26.5537(7)
<i>c</i> (Å)	13.849(4)	26.7924(8)
α (deg)	102.351(4)	90
β (deg)	103.394(4)	107.1700(10)
γ (deg)	111.187(4)	90
λ (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1615.7(8)	12916.6(6)
<i>F</i> (000)	387	6128
<i>Z</i>	2	8
<i>T</i> (K)	295	293
<i>D</i> (mg/m ⁻³)	1.422	1.550
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.335	0.977
R1 (all data)	0.0601	0.0612
wR2 [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.2035	0.1740
GOF	0.93	1.07

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) for [H₂L]ClO₄

Distances			
O5-C5	1.279(3)	C1-C2	1.510(5)
N1-C8	1.302(3)	C2-C7	1.384(4)
N1-C9	1.416(3)	C2-C3	1.389(4)
N2-C14	1.423(4)	C3-C4	1.398(4)
N2-N3	1.248(3)	C4-C8	1.421(4)
N4-C23	1.421(4)	N3-C15	1.425(4)
Angles			
C8-N1-C9	127.0(2)	C7-C6-C21	119.5(3)
N3-N2-C14	115.2(2)	C2-C7-C6	123.3(3)
N2-N3-C15	113.7(2)	N1-C8-C4	122.0(3)
C21-N4-C23	127.5(2)	N1-C9-C10	122.2(2)

Table 3. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) for compound [(L)₂Cu₂](ClO₄)₂

Distances			
Cu1-O1	1.949(3)	N1-N2	1.253(4)
Cu1-O2	1.929(3)	N3-C9	1.422(5)
Cu1-N2	2.832(3)	N3-C14	1.289(5)
Cu1-N3	1.961(3)	N4-C24	1.135(6)
Cu1-N5	2.657(4)	C8-C9	1.398(5)
Cu1-N6	1.937(3)	C14-C15	1.441(6)
N1-N2	1.272(5)	C15-C20	1.438(5)
N1-C1	1.410(6)	C19-C20	1.424(6)
Angles			
O1-Cu1-N2	102.41(11)	N2-C8-C9	115.2(4)
O1-Cu1-N3	88.93(12)	N2-C8-C13	124.4(3)
N2-Cu1-N3	69.16(11)	N3-C9-C8	117.7(3)
Cu1-N2-N1	138.1(2)	N3-C9-C10	122.5(3)
Cu1-N2-C8	99.6(2)	N3-C14-C15	123.3(4)
Cu1-N3-C9	118.7(2)	C14-C15-C20	121.4(3)
Cu1-N3-C14	121.3(3)	O1-C20-C15	122.3(4)
Cu1-O1-C20	117.2(2)	O1-C20-C19	120.0(3)

method. Hydrogen atoms, excepting H1a and H1b, were included for structure factor calculations after placing them at calculated positions. Atomic coordinates and isotropic thermal parameters of [H₂L]ClO₄ and [(L₂dial)₂Cu₂](ClO₄)₂ are given in Table 1.

Conclusion

Synthesis of multidentate ligands is important in terms of ion and molecular recognition in addition to synthesis of polynuclear complexes. Herein the synthesis and unequivocal characterization of new polydentate azoimine

ligand has been reported to initiate new type of host for ion and molecular recognition. On the other hand the new dinuclear Cu^{II} complex would open a new window to design the model complexes.

Supplementary materials

CCDC 1435249-1435250 for [H₂L]ClO₄ and [(L)₂Cu₂](ClO₄)₂ contain the supplementary crystallographic data respectively. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : +44 1223 336 033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk. Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version.

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